

XXI

International Conference on Building
Pathology and Constructions Repair

June 16th - 18th, 2025

Environmental Assessment of the Central Library and University Restaurant at the University of Brasília: Acoustic, Lighting and Thermal Comfort

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Abstract: Environmental comfort is a key factor in ensuring quality and productivity in built environments. It is comprised of four pillars: visual, acoustic, lighting, and thermal comfort. This study evaluates environmental comfort in two monumental buildings at the University of Brasília: the Central Library and the University Restaurant. Focusing on acoustic, lighting, and thermal aspects, the research aims to assess the performance of these heritage structures and compare them with existing standards, particularly NBR 15.575-1 and NBR 15.575-3 (ABNT, 2021) – Brazilian Performance Standard. The methodology included on-site measurements based on Brazilian and international norms, alongside user perception gathered through structured questionnaires. Results indicate that the Central Library performs well in acoustic and lighting aspects but shows thermal discomfort due to insufficient natural ventilation. The University Restaurant, however, demonstrates significant acoustic discomfort, moderate lighting conditions, and notable thermal dissatisfaction. The findings highlight the need for specific performance guidelines for monumental buildings that integrate technical evaluation with user experience.

Keywords: Comfort; acoustic comfort; lighting comfort; thermal comfort; performance standards;

1. INTRODUCTION

When designing an architectural project, it is essential to consider not only the aesthetics but also the user experience, as reflected in environmental comfort. Over time, the focus on heritage buildings has shifted from purely visual aspects to also valuing elements such as cultural identity and well-being. Environmental comfort, crucial for ensuring quality and productivity, comprises four key pillars: visual, acoustic, lighting, and thermal comfort. Although the perception of these factors is inherently subjective, standards have been developed to guarantee minimum acceptable levels for all users.

Visual comfort refers to an aesthetically pleasing environment, influenced by colors, textures, openings to the outside, the passage of natural light, and natural materials (Alves, 2012). Acoustic comfort, on the other hand, concerns the control of sounds and noise, regulated by standards such as NBR 15.575-1 (ABNT, 2021) and NBR 10.151 (ABNT, 2000). Regarding lighting comfort, it depends on factors such as solar radiation, humidity, and cloudiness, and is standardized by NBR ISO/CIE 8995 (2013) and NBR 15.575-1 (ABNT, 2021). Finally, thermal comfort refers to the balance of heat exchange between the body and the environment, aiming to provide well-being when these exchanges occur appropriately (Lamberts; Dutra; Pereira, 1997). This article addresses these concepts in relation to the Central Library (BCE) - Figure 1 - and the University Restaurant (RU) - Figure 2 - both located at the University of Brasília (UnB). Its objective is to present the

methodological procedures and the results obtained through questionnaires and the use of equipment for on-site measurements, aiming to assess the performance of these monumental buildings and serve as a reference for future performance standards.

Figure 1 - Facade of Central Library (BCE) of UnB.

Source: UnB (2024), modified by the authors.

Figure 2 - Facade of the Central Library of Brasília

Source: Personal archive of Galbinski (2017).

2. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURE

To conduct the analysis of the application of environmental comfort in modernist buildings, 2 (two) methodological procedures were used: 1) on-site measurements following technical standards; 2) questionnaires.

2.1 On-site Measurements

2.1.1 – Measurements and tests were conducted at both the Central Library (BCE) and the University Restaurant (RU) at the University of Brasília (UnB). These assessments focused on acoustic and lighting comfort. Thermal comfort was not measured directly; instead, it was evaluated exclusively through the questionnaire.

2.1.2 – Central Library (BCE)

Acoustic and lighting comfort measurements were conducted on-site after operating hours. The absence of users in the library facilitated the execution of the tests and allowed for more accurate results due to the lack of ambient interference. In this building, the impact sound insulation level test was prioritized, as airborne noise measurements would likely yield negligible values given the library's intrinsically quiet environment. The impact sound insulation level (L'_{nTw}) was measured using a *Bruel & Kjaer* tapping machine, in accordance with ISO 140-7 (2013) and NBR 15.575-3 (2013). This device uses mechanical hammers to strike the floor at a standardized rhythm to generate impact noise. A *Bruel & Kjaer* 2250 sound level meter was used to capture and measure the noise at five different points. Figure 3 shows both equipments.

Figure 3 - *Bruel & Kjaer* Tapping Machine and Model 2250 Sound Level Analyzer.

Regarding the measurement of lighting comfort at the BCE, 5 (five) parameters established in Annex B of NBR 15.575-1 (2013) were followed: 1) without the entry of external light; 2) with all artificial lighting fully activated; 3) at the center of the rooms; 4) without the presence of opaque obstructions; and 5) on a horizontal plane 0.80 meters above the floor level. The equipment used was the portable lux meter THAL-300 (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Portable lux meter THAL-300.

2.1.3 – University Restaurant (RU)

For the acoustic comfort measurements, the equivalent sound pressure level of the environment during use was recorded. The test was conducted on June 16, 2016, between 12:00 PM and 12:40 PM — peak hours at the University Restaurant (RU), when noise levels are typically highest — using also the *Bruel & Kjaer 2250* sound level meter. For the lighting comfort measurements, the same equipment and the same parameters described in item 2.1.2 were used, with measurements taken at twelve different points within the building.

2.2 Application of Questionnaires

Questionnaires were administered to users of both facilities, with 51 (fifty-one) questionnaires applied at the Central Library (BCE) and 50 (fifty) at the University Restaurant (RU), totaling 101 (one hundred and one) questionnaires. The corresponding questions are presented in section 3.2, where they are detailed.

2.2.1 – Central Library of UnB

The questionnaires at the Central Library were administered during peak hours, both during the day and at night. A total of 26 (twenty-six) questionnaires were completed in the afternoon, between 3:00 PM and 4:00 PM, and 25 (twenty-five) were completed in the evening, between 7:00 PM and 8:00 PM. Participants evaluated their perception of thermal, lighting, and acoustic comfort, assessing factors such as temperature, entry of light and wind, indoor lighting, the need for visual effort during reading, and their ability to concentrate in relation to local sounds and their impact. Finally, users listed 5 (five) factors that contributed to both comfort and discomfort within the environment.

2.2.2 – University Restaurant of UnB

The questionnaires at the University Restaurant were administered during peak hours, both during the day and at night. A total of 25 (twenty-five) questionnaires were completed in the afternoon, between 12:00 PM and 12:30 PM, and 25 (twenty-five) were completed in the evening, between 6:00 PM and 7:00 PM. Regarding thermal and lighting comfort and users' perceptions, the same questions from the BCE questionnaire were used. Additionally, participants were asked whether ambient noise influenced the volume of their conversations and, if so, what the noise source was, its impact, and whether it was still possible to understand the person they were speaking with despite the background noise.

3. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained from both the on-site measurements and the questionnaires.

3.1 On-site Measurements

3.1.1 – Central Library

The results of the impact sound insulation level test ($L'nTw$) were obtained using BZ 2250 software, covering the main frequency bands of 125 Hz, 250 Hz, 500 Hz, 1,000 Hz, and 2,000 Hz. The average measured value was 73.62 dB, which meets the minimum performance requirements established by NBR 15.575-3 (ABNT, 2021), stipulating that $L'nTw$ must remain above 55 dB for floor system of collective-use areas above the bedroom of autonomous housing units and 80 dB for floor system of autonomous housing units above the bedroom (Figure 5). Only the measurement at 250 Hz exceeded this threshold. Consequently, 80% of the results followed the standard, suggesting that the performance criteria for impact sound insulation in residential buildings may be appropriately extended to monumental-scale libraries.

Figure 5 - Impact Sound Insulation Level (L'nTw) of the Central Library (BCE).

Regarding lighting comfort, part 1 of the performance standard establishes a minimum illuminance level of 100 lux for living room, bedroom, bathroom and service area (ABNT, 2021). Based on measurements taken from 4 (four) points within the building, as shown in Figure 6, an average of 262.75 lux was obtained, which complies with the performance standard. However, this value is significantly below the minimum requirement set by ISO 8995 (2013), which recommends a minimum illuminance level of 500 lux.

Figure 6 - Illuminance Level of the BCE.

3.1.2 – University Restaurant

For the acoustic comfort measurements, a diagram like the one shown in Figure 7 was generated for each of the twenty-one measurement points. The x-axis of the graph displays the main sound frequencies (in Hz) recorded during the measurements, while the y-axis represents the corresponding sound pressure levels (in dB). The values LAFmax, LASmax, LASmin, and LAFmin represent the peak levels captured by the equipment

throughout the evaluation, with LAeq being the primary value used for analysis. Based on measurements taken at twenty-one points within the building, an average LAeq of 78.1 dB was recorded. According to the definition of housing units provided by the standard, the University Restaurant (RU) would be classified as a single housing unit, due to the absence of internal partitions. This classification conflates compliance with the performance standard, which does not provide a reference measure of sound pressure levels within a single housing unit. Therefore, for the purposes of this analysis, only NBR 10152 was used as the reference standard. The measured values exceeded the NBR 10.152 (1987) limits by approximately 60%.

Figure 7 - Spectral Distribution of Sound Pressure Levels (dB).

Regarding lighting comfort, the Brazilian performance standard establishes a minimum illuminance level of 100 lux for spaces such as dining halls, whereas ISO 8995 (2013) recommends a minimum of 200 lux. The average illuminance recorded across six dining halls was 160.83 lux, which meets the national performance standard but falls short of the international benchmark set by ISO 8995 (2013), as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Illuminance Level of the RU Dining Halls

When evaluating the 4 (four) ramps, structures for which both NBR 15.575-1 (2021) and ISO 8995 (2013) establish 100 lux as the minimum requirement, 50% of the ramps would not meet the standard, while in 2 (two) ramps, the illuminance level was satisfactory and exceeded the minimum required, as shown in the graph in **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.**

Figure 9 - Illuminance Level of the Ramps at the RU.

The alternative method for assessing acoustic comfort in these environments - based on user questionnaires - is presented in the following sections.

3.2 Evaluation of the Questionnaires

The following are the questions and results from the questionnaires administered at BCE and the RU.

3.3 Central Library (BCE)

The tables below show the questionnaires, and the results obtained at the Central Library (BCE).

Table 1 – Thermal Comfort - BCE

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. At this moment, do you perceive the environment to be:	Very cold	0	0	0
	Cold	0	0	0
	Neither cold nor hot	18	19	16
	Hot	55	50	60
	Very hot	27	31	24
Q2. Would you prefer the environment to be:	Much warmer	0	0	0
	Warmer	0	0	0
	Neither warmer nor cooler	8	8	8
	Cooler	82	81	84
	Much cooler	10	12	8
Q3. Do you observe direct sunlight inside the environment?	Yes	19	19	-
	No	81	81	-
	Yes	33	31	36

Q4. Do you perceive the entry of wind?	No	67	69	64
Q5. If yes, does the wind cause discomfort?	Yes	0	0	0
	No	100	100	100

Table 2 – Lighting Comfort - BCE

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. In your opinion, the natural light entering the environment is:	Very weak	4	4	-
	Weak	27	27	-
	Neither weak nor Strong	50	50	-
	Strong	19	19	-
	Very strong	0	0	-
Q2. How would you rate the lighting level in this room:	Very low	0	0	0
	Low	6	4	8
	Neither low nor high	49	58	40
	High	43	35	52
	Very high	2	4	0
Q3. You consider this environment to be:	Very Bright	8	8	8
	Bright	65	69	60
	Neither Bright nor dark	27	23	32
	Dark	0	0	0
	Very dark	0	0	0
Q4. Do you need to strain your eyes to perform activities?	Yes	6	4	8
	No	94	96	92
Q5. When reading, do you notice glare on the paper?	Yes	24	12	36
	No	75	88	60

Table 3 – Acoustic Comfort - BCE

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. Are there sounds that affect your concentration?	Yes	61	54	68
	No	39	46	32
Q2. If yes to the previous question, is this influence:	Positive	4	0	8
	Negative	35	23	48
	Neither positive nor negative	22	31	12
Q3. The sounds you identified in the previous question come from:	Vehicle traffic	2	0	4
	Activities outside the environment	29	27	32
	Conversations inside the environment	35	38	32
	Noise inside the environment	33	31	36
	Other:	6	4	8

Table 4 – Perception of the Environment - BCE

PERCEPTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT
Q1. What are the 5 things you identify that most contribute to comfort in this environment?
Q2. What are the 5 things you identify that contribute most to discomfort in this environment?

At the Central Library (BCE), acoustic comfort was identified as a moderate concern, particularly during evening hours. Users reported that interior sounds—primarily conversations and background noise—negatively affected their concentration. Although the building’s acoustic insulation was effective, with fewer than 30% of users perceiving external noise, 61% indicated that sound interfered with their focus, and 35% classified the impact as negative. These findings suggest that while insulation performance meets acceptable standards, the internal acoustic environment still requires improvement to ensure a higher level of comfort.

In terms of lighting comfort, only responses collected during the daytime were considered for the assessment of natural light. Approximately 80% of respondents rated the daylight as “neither weak nor strong,” “weak,” or “very weak,” indicating a predominant reliance on artificial lighting. Despite this, over 90% of users considered the overall illumination to be satisfactory, and fewer than 10% reported needing to strain their eyes while reading. However, during nighttime use, nearly 40% of respondents noted the presence of glare on the page, suggesting a localized issue likely related to the positioning or type of light fixtures.

Thermal comfort was the most critical issue reported by users. More than 80% considered the environment to be “hot” or “very hot,” and over 90% expressed a desire for the space to be cooler. Less than 20% perceived direct sunlight, which is advantageous in a space intended for reading. However, only 33% noticed any airflow—though all who did viewed it positively. The low perception of ventilation, combined with widespread thermal dissatisfaction, highlights the need for strategies to improve air circulation, either through passive design or mechanical systems.

3.4 University Restaurant (RU)

The tables below present the questionnaires and the results obtained at the University Restaurant (RU).

Table 5 – Thermal Comfort - RU

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. At this moment, do you perceive the environment to be:	Very cold	0	0	0
	Cold	0	0	0
	Neither cold nor hot	44	48	40
	Hot	52	48	56
	Very hot	4	4	4
Q2. Would you prefer the environment to be:	Much warmer	0	0	0
	Warmer	0	0	0
	Neither warmer nor cooler	20	20	20
	Cooler	64	68	60
	Much cooler	16	12	20
Q3. Do you observe direct sunlight inside the environment?	Yes	28	28	-
	No	72	72	-
Q4. Do you perceive the entry of wind?	Yes	44	48	40
	No	54	52	56
Q5. If yes, does the wind cause discomfort?	Yes	0	0	0
	No	100	100	100

Table 6 – Lighting Comfort - RU

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. In your opinion, the natural light entering the environment is:	Very weak	0	0	-
	Weak	24	24	-
	Neither weak nor Strong	64	64	-
	Strong	12	12	-
	Very strong	0	0	-
Q2. How would you rate the lighting level in this room:	Very low	0	0	0
	Low	16	16	16
	Neither low nor high	66	72	60
	High	16	8	24
	Very high	0	0	0
Q3. You consider this environment to be:	Very Bright	0	0	0
	Bright	32	28	36
	Neither Bright nor dark	58	64	52
	Dark	10	8	12
	Very dark	0	0	0
Q4. Do you need to strain your eyes to perform activities?	Yes	12	12	12
	No	88	88	88
Q5. When reading, do you notice glare on the paper?	Yes	-	-	-
	No	-	-	-

Table 7 – Acoustic Comfort - RU

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS	TOTAL (%)	DAYTIME (%)	NIGHTTIME (%)
Q1. Are there sounds that affect your concentration?	Yes	94	96	92
	No	6	4	8
Q2. If yes to the previous question, is this influence:	Positive	2	4	0
	Negative	68	60	76
	Neither positive nor negative	24	32	16
Q3. The sounds you identified in the previous question come from:	Vehicle traffic	6	0	12
	Activities outside the environment	14	8	20
	Conversations inside the environment	86	96	76
	Other:	16	8	24
Q4. Can you hear and clearly understand the voice of the person you are speaking with?	Yes	34	20	48
	No	4	4	4
	Somewhat	60	72	48
	I am not speaking with anyone	2	4	0

Table 8 – Perception of the Environment - RU

PERCEPTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT

Q1. What are the 5 things you identify that most contribute to comfort in this environment?

Q2. What are the 5 things you identify that contribute most to discomfort in this environment?

With respect to acoustic comfort, 94% of users reported that ambient noise influenced the volume of their conversations, with 68% perceiving this influence as negative. The primary sources of noise identified were overlapping conversations and external activities. Furthermore, only 34% of respondents stated that they were able to clearly understand the person they were speaking with, indicating a significant deficiency in the building's acoustic performance. These findings suggest that the University Restaurant (RU) does not offer an acoustically comfortable environment for its users.

In terms of lighting comfort, 65% of users rated the natural light as “neither weak nor strong,” “weak,” or “very weak,” while 58% described the overall environment as “neither bright nor dark.” Although the majority (88%) reported not needing to strain their eyes for routine activities—indicating a generally acceptable level of visual comfort—approximately 26% considered the environment “dark” or “very dark.” These responses suggest that certain areas, particularly ramps and lounges, require targeted improvements in artificial lighting, as corroborated by the on-site measurements.

Regarding thermal comfort, 56% of users described the environment as “hot” or “very hot,” and 80% expressed a preference for cooler conditions. Perceptions of airflow were mixed: 44% reported noticing ventilation, and all of them viewed it positively. This highlights the need to implement more effective passive or mechanical ventilation strategies to enhance thermal comfort in the RU.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of this study underscore the importance of evaluating environmental performance in monumental-scale buildings using criteria that are responsive to both the physical attributes of the space and the lived experiences of its users. At the Central Library (BCE) of the University of Brasília, strong performance was observed in terms of acoustic insulation and lighting comfort, indicating that some normative parameters established for residential buildings may be partially applicable or adaptable to monumental public structures. However, thermal comfort emerged as a significant concern, with high levels of user dissatisfaction and limited perception of natural ventilation, highlighting the need for targeted improvements in this domain.

In contrast, the University Restaurant (RU) presented more critical deficiencies. The acoustic environment was deemed inadequate, with substantial noise interference reported by users, which impaired communication and reduced auditory comfort. Thermal comfort was also evaluated negatively by the majority of respondents, while lighting comfort achieved only moderate results, with specific areas—such as ramps and lounges—requiring improvements in artificial illumination.

These findings support the conclusion that large-scale, collective-use buildings demand performance guidelines tailored to their unique architectural, functional, and symbolic characteristics. It is recommended that future standards for this category of building integrate both quantitative measurements and qualitative user feedback to ensure environments that are not only technically compliant but also comfortable, inclusive, and aligned with their social purpose.

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